

NMP_10perc_1219

Sample Name NMP_10perc_1219
Date collected 2025-12-19

Pulse sequence PROTON
Solvent d2o

Temperature 28.5
Spectrometer varian300.chem.byu.edu-inova300
Study owner marsh81

NMP_10perc_1219

Sample Name NMP_10perc_1219 Pulse sequence PROTON Temperature 28.5 Study owner marsh81
 Date collected 2025-12-19 Solvent d2o Spectrometer varian300.chem.byu.edu-inova300 marsh81

NMP_10perc_1219

SAMPLE	wet	n
<hr/>		
date	Dec 19 2025	SPECIAL
solvent	d2o	
file	/opt/nmrdata/mars	temp
h81/NMP_10perc_1219_202	51219_01/PROTON_06.fid	28.5
		gain
		30
		spin
		0
		hst
		0.008
		pw90
		11.500
ACQUISITION	alfa	10.000
<hr/>		
sw	4799.6	FLAGS
at	3.414	
np	32768	il
fb	3000	n
bs	32	in
ss	4	nw
d1	20.000	dp
nt	8	y
ct	8	hs
		nn
		PROCESSING
		lb
		0.50
TRANSMITTER		fn
		131072
<hr/>		
tn	H1	DISPLAY
sfrq	299.972	
tof	300.0	sp
tpwr	56	-599.9
pw	3.833	wp
		4799.5
		rfl
		600.0
		rfp
		0
DECOUPLER		rp
		-56.2
		lp
		-2.2
<hr/>		
dn	C13	PLOT
dof	0	
dm	nnn	
decwave	W40_pfgAuSW	wc
dpwr	28	234
dmf	26316	sc
		8
		vs
		4739
		th
		32
PRESATURATION	ai	cdc
		ph
<hr/>		
satmode	n	
Plotname: PROTON_06_plot02--		